

Research

An efficient method to solve minimum spanning tree problem using graph theory and improved ant colony optimization algorithm

K.P.O.Niluminda^{1*}, E.M.U.S.B.Ekanayake²

^{1,2}Department of Physical Sciences, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, Mihinthale, Sri Lanka

Abstract: A specific type of graph G is a spanning tree. A spanning tree is produced when all of the vertices of a connected undirected graph G are connected by the fewest number of edges possible. For a graph, there may be several such spanning trees. However, the term "Minimum Spanning Tree" (MST) refers to a connected, edge-weighted, undirected network that has all of its vertices connected, is cycle-free, and has the least amount of total edge weight. Several algorithms have been developed by researchers to find MST. Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms are famous algorithms developed to find the MST of an undirected connected graph. In 1990, the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) approach developed and it has been solely motivated by the foraging behavior of ant colonies. Ants are eusocial insects that want to thrive and survive as a group rather than as a single species. Pheromones, touch, and sound are the main means of communication between them. The ants release pheromones, which are organic chemical substances that cause other members of their species to act socially. In this study, we proposed a new probability-based algorithm to find the MST of undirected connected graphs using an improved ACO algorithm. The proposed method is then shown using numerical examples and compared with existing MST algorithms. We get outcomes that are on par with those of the algorithms developed by Prim and Kruskal.

Keywords: Ant colony optimization, Minimum spanning tree, Pheromones, Prim's algorithm, Undirected graph

*Corresponding Author: kponiluminda@gmail.com

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Introduction

For a graph (network) to be a spanning tree, all of its vertices (nodes) must be connected by edges (lines) that are one fewer than those of the supplied graph. This results in a cycle-free network since all of the vertices are covered by lines that are exactly one fewer than those of the given graph. Since any connected and directionless graph may have at least one spanning tree with the same amount of nodes as a network and lines one less than the supplied graph, we can define a spanning tree generally as a tree without even any cycles. The given graph can thus never be a disconnected graph. A spanning tree whose total number of nodes is minimal is known as a MST. When building networks, MSTs

are helpful since they show how to link a group of locations with the least amount of wire overall. The sensible method of grouping points in space into natural groupings is to use MSTs.

ACO is a population-based probabilistic search technique for addressing various combinatorial optimization issues. The foundation of ACO is the idea of stigmergy, which is the indirect interaction that occurs when a population of members interacts with their surroundings. Ants' communication while foraging is an illustration of stigmergy: ants influence one another's behavior by leaving behind pheromone trails, which they use as a kind of indirect communication. This straightforward method of inter-ant communication gives rise to the complicated skills and behaviors of the colonies [1]. Marco Dorigo [2] suggested the Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm in his 1992 doctoral thesis. It is a technique for figuring out the straightest line between an origin and an endpoint. The way ants go from their nest (colony) to a food source in quest of food is the model for this activity. Their approach helps determine the most efficient path between the source and the final destination. With the use of the probability-based Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm, a variety of optimization issues may be resolved. The traveling salesman problem, the shortest path problem, the various traffic problem, the work schedules problem, and others are examples of problems.

The MSTs of the graph may be found using a variety of approaches. Depending on how they are implemented, these algorithms can be classified into two categories. Examples of MST include Line (Edge)-based and Node (Vertices)-based. Algorithms that use lines include Kruskal and Reverse Delete, whereas those that use nodes are Prim and Dijkstra. The earliest known approach for identifying a MST was created by Czech scholar Otakar Borvka [3] in 1926. This algorithm is referred to as Borvka's algorithm. Then, Prim [4] and Kruskal [5] produced two unique algorithms. One of the approaches was developed by Robert C. Prim in 1957 after Vojtech Jarnk presented it in 1930 [4]. It was rediscovery by Edsger W. Dijkstra in 1959, and he gave it the name Prim's algorithm [4]. Another algorithm, titled Kruskal's algorithm, was released by Joseph Kruskal [5] in 1956. G. Cong [6] researched the locality behavior of MST algorithms. The new cycle detection method was presented by Prantik Biswas [7] in 2006. S. Ruzika [8] surveyed multi-objective MST problems. E.M.U.S.B.Ekanayake [4] proposed a new method to find MST using a modified ACO algorithm. K.P.O.Niluminda [9] presented a new technique to solve MST problem using a weight adjacency matrix. Additionally, Paryati [10], Abhilasha R. [11], Arindam Dey [12], A. Sayli [13], Peace Ayegba [14], Murat [15], Saibal Majumder [16], S. Pettie [17], D. Vijayalakshmir [18] and H. Gabow [19] proposed several algorithms to address MST problems. This study focuses on finding a new alternative method to determine MST of any directionless connected graph using graph theory concepts and an improved ACO algorithm. The outcomes of several instances are comparative analysis with Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms at the end of this paper.

Preliminaries

This section discusses some basic definitions related to this proposed algorithm and the steps of Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms.

Spanning Tree

A spanning tree is a tree that joins every node in the graph $G = (V, E)$ with the fewest amount of edges.

Minimum Spanning Tree (MST)

A particular kind of spanning tree is known as an MST, where the sum of all edge weights is kept as minimal as possible. In the case of a connected undirected graph $G(V, E)$, the spanning tree is properly defined as $G(V, E')$ & $E' \subseteq E$. Equation (1) describes how much weight the minimal spanning tree has.

$$W(T) = \sum_{e \in T} W(E') \quad (1)$$

Prim's Algorithm

For figuring out whether the MST is any linked network undirected graph, Prim's algorithm is the well-known and renowned approach. Additionally, this approach uses a node-based technique. The steps of Prim's algorithm are mentioned below [20]:

- Step 1: Inspect all the edges that link to any beginning vertex, then select the one with the least weight to add to the tree.
- Step 2: Examine all of the tree's edges that are joined to it but do not have both of its vertices there.
- Step 3: Add it to the tree by picking the one with the minimum weight.
- Step 4: Up until every vertex is included in the tree, repeat step 2.

Kruskal's Algorithm

A link with the lowest weight allowed that joins any pair of trees in the forest is found by Kruskal's technique, which utilizes a MST algorithm. A connected weighted network's MST is found using a greedy approach in graph theory, which adds rising price lines in every step while it searches for the MST. The overall weight of all the links in the tree is reduced, and as a result, it discovers a subset of the edges that creates a tree with every vertex. Following is a list of the steps in the Kruskal algorithm [20]:

- Step 1: Every edge should be sorted from lightweight to heavyweight.
- Step 2: Add the edge with the lightest weight to the spanning tree.
- Step 3: The edge should be rejected if adding it resulted in a loop.
- Step 4: Continue to add edges until all vertices have been reached.

Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) Algorithm

An approach to probability-based path-finding that is inspired by ant behavior is called an ant colony optimization method. When ants leave their residence (let's say, city i) they employ pheromones to find food resources (say, city j). The probabilistic transition rule and the pheromone update rule are applicable if an ant k wishes to relocate to city j from city i. The Transition rule and Pheromone update rule equations are lists in below [21].

Transition Rule

According to equation (2), the ant colony optimization algorithm's probabilistic transition rule is as follows. The quantity of pheromone on element between cities i and j is indicated by φ_{ij} , and its heuristic value is indicated by ε_{ij} . P_{ij}^k signifies the probability branch of kth ant from ith city to jth city. The parameters are α and β and there between zero and one (i.e. $0 \leq \alpha, \beta \leq 1$) [21, 22].

$$P_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \frac{[\varphi_{ij}]^\alpha [\varepsilon_{ij}]^\beta}{\sum_{z \in Allowed_k} [\varphi_{iz}]^\alpha [\varepsilon_{iz}]^\beta} & j \in Allowed_k \\ 0; & Otherwise \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Pheromone Update Rule

Equations (3), (4), and (5) show how the local update rule for pheromone trails. Here, d_k stands for the optimum path's distance. Usually set to 1, the parameter ω controls how much pheromone is deposited [21, 22].

$$\varphi_{ij}(t + 1) = \rho \cdot \varphi_{ij}(t) + \Delta\varphi_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta\varphi_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^Z \Delta\varphi_{ij} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta\varphi_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \frac{\omega}{d_k} & \text{if ant } k \text{ travels on city } (i, j) \\ 0 & ; \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Methodology

The following list of stages is the proposed algorithm. This suggested approach includes a few steps. This proposed methodology can be used to determine the MST of any undirected connected graph.

Step 1: Use the below improved ACO algorithm to determine the route based on the probabilities of each vertex and rearrange them in ascending order.

$$i.e. P_{ij} = \frac{w_{ijTotal} - w_{ij}}{\sum(w_{ijTotal} - w_{ij})} \quad (6)$$

Here, w_{ij} is the edge weight from i^{th} node to j^{th} node and $w_{ijTotal}$ is the total edge weight.

Step 2: Calculate the number of Deleting Edges (#DE) using the following equation.

$$i.e. \#DE = E_{Total} - n_{Total} + 1 \quad (7)$$

Here, E_{Total} and n_{Total} represent the total number of edges and nodes in the graph respectively.

Step 3: Remove the #DE calculate in step 2, and start from the minimum probability route.

Step 4: If the resulting graph is disconnected, connect those sub-graphs using the possible maximum probability route.

Step 5: If a graph has a loop, delete this loop by removing the minimum probability route.

The flow chart representation of the above algorithm is present in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Flow chart of proposed method

Results & Discussion

Under this sub-topic, solve some illustrative instances using the proposed algorithm and compare results with Prim’s and Kruskal’s algorithms.

Ex. 1

Fig. 1: Undirected connected graph_1

Step 1:

The route based on the probabilities of each vertex of the Fig. 2 graph is represented in Table 1 in ascending order.

Step 2:

The above graph of Figure 2 has 10 edges ($E_{Total} = 10$) and 5 nodes($n_{Total} = 5$).

So, the number of deleting edges (#DE) can be calculated as follows:

$$\#DE = E_{Total} - n_{Total} + 1 = 10 - 5 + 1 = 6 \text{ (Deleting Edges)}$$

Table 1: Route-based probabilities of the Fig. 2 graph in ascending order

No	Edge Name	Probability (P_{ij})	No	Edge Name	Probability (P_{ij})
1	DE	0.0850	6	BD	0.1013
2	BC	0.0947	7	AC	0.1046
3	AE	0.0980	8	AB	0.1046
4	CE	0.0980	9	CD	0.1046
5	EB	0.1013	10	AD	0.1078

Steps 3:

Fig. 3: After apply step 3

Step 4:

Fig. 4: After apply step 4

Step 5:

Fig. 5: Minimum Spanning Tree of figure 1 graph

By following the proposed algorithm step by step, the graph in Fig. 4 can obtain. That is the MST of the Fig. 2 graph, and the total weight of MST is 8.

Ex. 2 [20]

Fig. 6: Undirected connected graph_2

Step 1:

The route based on the probabilities of each vertex of the Fig. 6 graph is represented in Table 2 in ascending order.

Step 2:

The above graph of Fig. 6 has 13 edges ($E_{Total} = 13$) and 8 nodes ($n_{Total} = 8$). So, the number of deleting edges (#DE) can be calculated as follows:

$$\#DE = E_{Total} - n_{Total} + 1 = 13 - 8 + 1 = 6 \text{ (Deleting Edges)}$$

Table 2: Route-based probabilities of the Fig. 6 graph in ascending order

No	Edge Name	Probability (P_{ij})	No	Edge Name	Probability (P_{ij})
1	af	0.0682	8	bc	0.0803
2	gh	0.0712	9	de	0.0803
3	ef	0.0727	10	gf	0.0803
4	dg	0.0727	11	ab	0.0818
5	ah	0.0742	12	ch	0.0818
6	bh	0.0758	13	eg	0.0818
7	cd	0.0788			

Step 3:

Fig. 7: Minimum Spanning Tree of figure 5 graph

It is possible to obtain the graph shown in Fig. 7 by carefully following the suggested procedure. That is the MST shown in Fig. 6's graph, and its overall weight is 12.

Comparative Analysis of the Proposed Method

Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms are used in this subsection to compare the results of the aforementioned Examples 1 and 2.

Table 3: Comparative analysis of Ex. 1 and 2 with Prim's, Kruskal's, and Proposed Algorithms

Example No.	Prim's Algorithm	Kruskal's Algorithm	Proposed Algorithm
Ex.1	8	8	8
Ex.2	12	12	12

Fig. 8: The graphical representation of comparative analysis of Ex.1 and 2

Table 3 compares the results of Ex. 1 and 2 with those obtained using Prim's, Kruskal's, and the proposed algorithms, and Fig. 8 displays a bar graph of the results. For example, 1 total overall weight is equal to 8 and in example 2 it is 12. By comparison to Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms in both algorithms, outcomes are the same as the proposed method algorithm. In examples 1 and 2, the total overall weight is 8 and 12 respectively. Every bar graph in the illustration in Fig. 8 is the same height in those instances. When compared to Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms, both methods' results are similar to those of the suggested technique. In figure 8 graph every bar graphs are the same height in those examples.

Conclusion

A spanning tree of a connected, undirected graph is a subgraph of graph G that connects every node in the graph. A spanning tree that has a weight smaller or equivalent to the weight of each other feasible spanning tree is referred to as an MST for a weighted, linked, undirected graph. Several spanning trees may exist in a single network. Numerous algorithms have been proposed in the literature to find the MST of connected, directionless graphs. In these circumstances, two well-known algorithms are Prim's and Kruskal's.

By combining graph theory ideas with an enhanced ACO algorithm, this work offered a novel alternative approach for determining the MST of any directionless linked graph. Comparative analysis using Prim's and Kruskal's methods is done on the results of several occurrences. When the network has a large number of nodes, this new approach is simpler and easier to implement than other current techniques. Two illustrated examples are used to illustrate the new suggested method. When compared to Prim's and Kruskal's methods, the same results can get, and the research also introduced a novel, easy method for quickly and accurately finding the MST of an undirected connected weight graph.

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